

UKRAINE CRISIS: LITMUS TEST FOR INDIA'S FOREIGN AND ECONOMIC POLICY

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“There are neither permanent friends nor permanent enemies in international relations, only permanent interests.”

- Lord Palmerston

Introduction

Foreign policy of a country is never in a vacuum; it owes its formulation to several variables and constants like its history, geography, security dynamics, culture, economic strength and political discourse¹. The primary determinant of the any foreign policy continues to be National Interest, Strategic Culture, and Security Apparatus. While the national interest of a country is a comparatively long-term constant, its strategic culture is a medium-term phenomenon, subject to change with changing perceptions of the incumbents or the entry of a new lot of policymakers².

India's foreign policy since independence has focussed at ensuring strategic autonomy by avoiding alignment with any particular power bloc, while maintaining friendly relations with diverse nations and group³.With its rapidly expanding economy, growing military strength, and influential diplomatic initiatives, India in new millennium and more specifically in the Modi era has become a pivotal player in shaping the global political landscape. Through its active participation in regional and global organizations such as the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) and the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa) group, as well as its engagement with major global forums like the

United Nations India under Modi has been able to influence decision-making and policy discussions on a wide range of global issues.

India's strategic considerations have been significantly influenced by the evolving geopolitical landscape, especially in its immediate neighbourhood. The rise of China, terrorism, security challenges in South Asia, and the need to maintain stability in the region are critical factors shaping India's foreign policy. With United States as the only superpower and resurgence of Russia as a major player⁴, India while pursuing its national interests is faced with the challenge of maintaining a delicate balance between the two on one side and ensuring its strategic autonomy on the other especially after global economic slowdown courtesy COVID and ongoing Russia-Ukraine crisis.

The Russia-Ukraine war in particular has led to a significant shift in geopolitical dynamics, where the West led by US stood strongly behind Ukraine supporting it both in terms of military hardware and economic aid besides imposing several economic sanctions on Russia while on the other side, Russia has turned towards China for support and strategic cooperation including at UN⁵. India, with its traditional ties with Russia and its growing partnership with the United States, finds itself walking a tightrope as it navigates its relations with both the prominent powers during the war in Ukraine. India's position on Ukraine draws from the complexities of the relationship, and the evolving balance of power between Russia-China on one side and others of which US is the central pole.

To further highlight the gravity of the diplomatic dilemma that India encountered during the ongoing Ukraine crisis as tilting towards one would have affected its national strategic interest both in short and long term, there is a need to delve into the strategic relations that India has both with Russia and US, its energy security needs and implications of emerging world order especially threat China poses to regional peace and stability with its strategic alliances and hegemonial tendencies.

Indo- Russia: Strategic Partnership: Russia has been a traditional ally of India. India-Russia relations have been historically strong, characterized by a deep-rooted strategic partnership that has withstood global political changes over several decades. The foundation of this relationship was laid with the Indo-Soviet Treaty of Friendship and Cooperation⁶ signed in 1971. Since the signing of "Declaration on the India-Russia Strategic Partnership" in October 2000, India-Russia ties have acquired a qualitatively new character with enhanced levels of cooperation in almost all areas of the bilateral relationship including political,

security, defence, trade and economy, science & technology, culture, and people-to-people ties.

Over the decades, both nations have developed strong defence ties and have been cooperating and supporting each other's at various multinational forums like United Nations besides being part of other regional and trans regional grouping like BRICS and SCO. The partnership has evolved to reflect the changing geopolitical landscape, with both countries adjusting their foreign policies while retaining the essence of their strategic alliance. Some of the key aspects of Indo-Russia partnership that have direct bearing on India's strategic interests are :-

- Defence and Military Cooperation has been the cornerstone of bilateral relations. Russia has been a major supplier of defence equipment to India for decades⁷. This cooperation is multifaceted, involving various aspects such as defence equipment sales including advanced military hardware like fighter jets, submarines including nuclear, joint military exercises, strategic dialogues, and collaboration in defence technology.
- Russia, with its vast reserves of oil and natural gas and a major supplier to India⁸; thus, critical to India's energy security needs. Indian companies have invested in Russian oil fields, and there are long-term contracts for the supply of crude oil and liquefied natural gas (LNG) from Russia to India. Russia and India are also exploring the possibility of India storing part of its strategic petroleum reserves in Russia, which would be a unique arrangement enhancing India's energy security.
- Russia is a key partner in India's civilian nuclear energy program⁹. Russian companies have been involved in the supply of nuclear fuel and the construction of nuclear reactors in India. The Kudankulam Nuclear Power Plant in Tamil Nadu, built with Russian assistance, is a prominent example of this cooperation.
- Russia has provided critical support in terms of technology transfer and expertise, which has been vital in the development of India's indigenous space capabilities, including its satellite and launch vehicle programs. It has been a key partner in India's ambitious human spaceflight program and Gaganyaan mission which witness unparalleled cooperation between ISRO and Roscomos¹⁰.
- Indo-Russian economic ties, while historically overshadowed by their defence and strategic partnership, have been steadily evolving and diversifying. The trade volume

between India and Russia has been growing, but it is still below its potential compared to their strategic partnership.

- India and Russia, as major global players, frequently align their positions on various global issues within multinational forums. This alignment reflects their shared perspectives on international law, sovereignty, and a multipolar world order.
- Another key aspect of this strategic relationship is the cultural and people-to-people connections between Russia and India are an integral and vibrant part of their bilateral relationship. These ties, fostered over decades, have contributed significantly to mutual understanding and friendship between the two nations.

India-Russia relations, despite their long-standing strategic partnership, are not without areas of divergence and challenges. The evolving global geopolitical landscape, especially with the increasing closeness of Russia with China and shift in the Pakistan-Russia relationship has forced New Delhi to be flexible with its foreign policy and is looking beyond Russia. Similarly, India's deepening strategic and defence ties with Western countries, particularly the United States, through initiatives like the Quad (Quadrilateral Security Dialogue) involving the U.S., Japan, and Australia, may be viewed with apprehension by Russia. These divergences and challenges stem from changing geopolitical dynamics, national interests, and global issues.

In addition, with Russia facing sanctions from Western countries¹¹, particularly after events like its annexation of Crimea in 2014 and more recently due to the conflict in Ukraine, there are implications for countries engaging in defence trade with Russia. India, for instance, faces the risk of secondary sanctions under laws like the Countering America's Adversaries Through Sanctions Act (CAATSA) by the United States.

Indo-US Relations: Evolving Geo-Strategic Alignment: The geopolitical landscape has witnessed a seismic shift in India-US relations, evolving from the Cold War era's non-alignment policy to the current strategic partnerships. India and the US have seen a growth in convergence of their interest in the last one and a half decade. However, a new shift in the relations took place soon after Narendra Modi took oath as Prime Minister of India. The two countries guided convergence in democratic values, have strengthened their strategic partnership across multiple domains, including defence, counterterrorism, trade, and technology. Agreements such as the Logistics Exchange Memorandum of Agreement

(LEMOA) and the Communications Compatibility and Security Agreement (COMCASA) have facilitated enhanced defence cooperation.

- “New Framework for India US Defence Cooperation¹²”, now designated as as Major Defence Partnership (MDP) in 2016 has led to comprehensive, enduring and mutually beneficial defence partnership between the two nations. Defence procurements from the US have grown to around US\$ 21 billion also, several agreements like Logistics Exchange Memorandum of Association (August 2016); Memorandum of Intent between the U.S. defence Innovation Unit (DIU) and the Indian defence Innovation Organization – Innovation for defence Excellence (2018); Communications Compatibility and Security Agreement (September 2018); Industrial Security Agreement (December 2019); Basic Exchange and Cooperation Agreement (October 2020) have taken this relationship t strategic levels.
- Bilateral military exercises and defence exchanges are important aspect of deepening military-to-military cooperation¹³. The two countries now conduct more bilateral exercises with each other than they do with any other country. Bilateral and regional exercises includes : Yudh Abhyas (Army); Vajra Prahar (Special Forces); RIMPAC; In November 2020, Royal Australian Navy joined the U.S.-India-Japan MALABAR Naval Exercise held in the Bay of Bengal and the Arabian Sea. Both sides have conducted a number of PASSEX with the US carrier groups in the Indian Ocean Region.
- A shared recognition of the importance of a free and open Indo-Pacific is a cornerstone of strategic convergence between the two nations. Both India and the US are committed to countering the influence of authoritarian regimes in the region. Shared concerns about China's rise and its assertive actions have led to an alignment of interests in the Indo-Pacific. The convergence in strategic outlook is reflected in efforts to enhance interoperability and share defence technologies. The QUAD, comprising India, the US, Japan, and Australia, has emerged as a key forum for regional collaboration, emphasizing the centrality of democratic values in shaping the Indo-Pacific's future.
- Besides defence, growth in bilateral trade and economic interdependence has been a backbone of Indo-US relations¹⁴which is now the second largest trading partner.

Bilateral trade in goods and services stood at US\$ 128 billion in 2023 seeing almost eight percent jump from last year.

- India and the U.S. have also a long history of cooperation in the civil space arena. Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) has been actively pursuing civilian space cooperation with the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)¹⁵. On commercial front, ISRO has launched more than 200 satellites from US, on-board Polar Satellite Launch Vehicle (PSLV), as co passengers.
- Cooperation in multilateral forums such as the United Nations further underscores the shared commitment to global peace and stability. As both nations navigate the complex geopolitics of the 21st century, continued collaboration in addressing emerging threats and challenges remains paramount. At the Leaders' Summit on Climate held during April 22-23, 2021, the United States and India launched a new high-level partnership, the "U.S.- India Climate and Clean Energy Agenda 2030 Partnership," which envisages bilateral cooperation on strong actions in the current decade to meet the goals of the Paris Agreement.

The Dragon Factor: China's rapid economic growth and development over the past few decades have positioned it as a key player in the global economy¹⁶. With the world's largest population and the second largest economy, China has become a major trade partner for many countries around the world. However, China's economic expansion has also raised concerns about its trade practices and allegations of intellectual property theft, which have led to tensions with the US and other nations.

Sino-Indian relations are marked by a complex interplay of cooperation, competition, and conflict. The most prominent and persistent issue is the long-standing border dispute¹⁷. The lack of a clearly demarcated border along the Line of Actual Control (LAC) has led to several stand-offs and confrontations, most notably the 1962 war and more recent skirmishes in regions like Doklam and Galwan Valley¹⁸.

India and China have competing strategic interests. Both nations aspire to be regional leaders, often resulting in competition for influence in South Asia, Southeast Asia, and the Indian Ocean Region. This includes competing infrastructure and connectivity projects like India's Act East policy and China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). China's close ties with Pakistan, including its investment in the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) which passes through disputed territories claimed by India, is a major concern for India¹⁹. The

Indian Ocean Region is another area of strategic competition, with India concerned about China's increasing maritime presence and the development of port facilities in countries like Sri Lanka, Pakistan, and Myanmar, perceived as part of a "String of Pearls" strategy to encircle India

On global issues, India and China often find themselves on opposite sides, particularly in forums like the United Nations Security Council. Their differing stances on issues like human rights, trade policies, and international law reflect broader ideological and strategic divergences.

China and Russia have also strengthened their ties in recent years, with both countries expressing mutual interests in countering what they perceive as unilateralism and hegemony in international relations. The two nations have engaged in joint military exercises, economic partnerships, and diplomatic coordination on global issues. This new alliance has the potential to dramatically alter the global balance of power. A strengthened alliance between Russia and China might influence the dynamics in Central Asia, affecting India's interests in the region.

This partnership between Russia and China may also have economic implications for India. Both Russia and China are major players in the global economy, and their collaboration could shape trade and investment patterns. India, as a growing economy, would need to carefully assess and adapt to changes in the global economic landscape resulting from such an alliance.

From a geopolitical and regional stability perspective, China's increasing assertiveness in the South China Sea²⁰ coupled with militarization of disputed islands and its aggressive territorial claims have raised concerns about its willingness to challenge the existing international order and threaten stability in the region. Its expansionist policies in the region have caused alarm among its neighbouring countries like India and the US. Also, China's growing influence in global governance institutions, such as the United Nations and the World Trade Organization²¹, has also prompted the other nations like India and US to take a more proactive approach in countering China's agenda.

As China seeks to establish itself as a global superpower, the India recognizes the need to ensure that China's rise is balanced with its commitment to international rules and norms. Any geopolitical shifts in the region can have repercussions for its immediate

neighbours. Additionally, it could impact India's relationships with other countries, given the interconnectivity of global geopolitics.

The Balancing Act: Diplomacy at Play: Ukraine crisis presented significant diplomatic and economic challenges globally, and India under Prime Minister Narendra Modi's leadership navigated these challenges by prioritizing strategic autonomy and safeguarding its economic and national interests. India's approach to balancing its act in the Russia-Ukraine crisis has been characterized by diplomatic finesse and strategic pragmatism. Its response to the Russian invasion of Ukraine has been distinctive among the major democracies and among U.S. strategic partners. Despite its discomfort with war, New Delhi has adopted a studied public neutrality toward Russia²². It has abstained from successive votes in the UN Security Council, General Assembly, and Human Rights Council that condemned Russian aggression in Ukraine.

Under Modi, India has adeptly navigated its relationships with both the U.S.-led Western bloc and Russia, leveraging these ties to its advantage in various aspects of international relations and national development. Some of the key aspect of India's comprehensive actions and policies that includes both foreign and economic which have helped it sail through the current global crisis and make itself heard in the international forum are: -

- **Maintaining Strategic Autonomy.** A key principle guiding India's foreign policy under Modi is strategic autonomy²³, avoiding alignment with any single major power bloc and making decisions based on national interests. India's multi-alignment approach, engaging with all major powers on equal footing, has been evident in its interactions with both the West and Russia. India has maintained a balanced stance on issues sensitive to Russia, such as the situation in Ukraine, reflecting its strategic autonomy.
- **Neutral Diplomatic Stance:** India maintained a position of neutrality throughout the crisis. While calling for peace and dialogue, India abstained from voting on United Nations resolutions condemning Russia's actions, balancing its long-standing ties with Russia and its growing relations with Western nations²⁴.
- **Maximising Global and Regional Forums:** India uses global and regional forums to engage with both Western countries and Russia, often acting as a bridge between differing viewpoints. India's as host of G20 summit, has been strategic and proactive,

using the platform to build consensus on various global issues and has been able to position itself as a major voice for emerging and developing economies, advocating for a more equitable and balanced global order besides advancing its national interests²⁵.

- **Strategic Partnership With US:** Besides efforts being made to increase trade and investment flows with Western countries resulting in US emerging as one of India's largest trading partners, Modi government has significantly strengthened strategic ties with the U.S²⁶, particularly in defence and security. Key agreements like the Communications Compatibility and Security Agreement (COMCASA) and the Basic Exchange and Cooperation Agreement (BECA) have been signed, enhancing military cooperation and strategic alignment.
- **Maintaining Strategic Relations with Russia:** Russia continues to be a major supplier of defence equipment to India. Deals like the S-400 missile defence system acquisition illustrate the ongoing defence cooperation despite potential U.S. sanctions.
- **Operation Ganga:** Indian government under Modi, undertook "Operation Ganga" to successfully evacuate about 23000 Indian citizens and 147 foreign nationals belonging to 18 countries from Ukraine²⁷. This operation was notable for its scale and efficiency. It showcased India's diplomatic and political weight when it ensured temporary ceasefire by Russia, closure of Ukrainian airspace, and invoking neighbouring countries like Poland, Hungary, Slovakia, Romania, and Moldova, from where these students were airlifted. The success of "Operation Ganga" was a testament to the government's commitment to the safety and welfare of its citizens abroad, showcasing India's capability to conduct large-scale evacuation operations under challenging circumstances.
- **Articulating National Interests:** India consistently articulated its decisions as being based on national interests, particularly in international forums, emphasizing its independent foreign policy. Reply of India's external Affairs minister S Jaishankar in the Rajya Sabha to a question on the situation in Ukraine, where he said "*India's foreign policy decisions are made in line with national interests and the country is guided by our thinking, our views, our interests*" aptly describes the rationale and thought behind India's response to the crisis.

- **Ensuring Energy Security:** Despite sanctions imposed by US and EU, India in its national interest increased its energy imports from Russia²⁸, especially during global disruptions, benefiting from discounted rates and strengthening energy ties.
- **Prioritising Development Agenda:** In its relations with both blocs, India prioritized its domestic development agenda, seeking technology, investments, and partnerships that align with its goals like Make in India, Digital India, and Clean Energy initiatives.

Safeguarding Economic Interest and Ensuring Energy Security

During the Ukraine-Russia war, India faced significant challenges in managing its energy security, particularly as the conflict led to global disruptions and leading to higher prices and potential shortages leading to inflation and a slowdown in economic growth. India's approach to ensuring energy security during this period involved a multifaceted strategy²⁹. It pursued its own national interests by diversifying its sources of defence equipment and energy imports. India made a conscious change in its strategic outlook when it started reducing its reliance on Russian defence equipment and has increased its engagement with the US and other Western countries in defence and security cooperation. Some of the significant proactive actions of the Modi government to ensure energy security while safeguarding its economic interest during this ongoing crisis are:

- **Diversifying Oil Imports:** As the world's third-largest consumer of oil, India's energy choices had the potential to influence global oil prices and market dynamics. India diversified its crude oil imports to mitigate the risks associated with over-reliance on specific region. While the Middle East remained a major source, India increased its imports from other countries, including Russia, which offered crude oil at discounted rates due to Western sanctions. As of 2023, Russian imports grew to \$31 billion, compared to just \$2.5 billion in the previous year thus accounted for 39% of India's overall crude imports, a significant increase from 16% in 2022. By forging ahead with its energy cooperation with Russia, India sent a signal to the international community regarding its strategic autonomy and ability of stand its ground in its national interest.
- **Leveraging Strategic Petroleum Reserves:** The Indian government, recognizing the importance of maintaining stability in the oil market during this period of geopolitical tension, deployed its Strategic Petroleum Reserves (SPR) which is approximately 5.33 million metric tonnes (MMT) or 38 million barrels of crude oil to contain market

volatility. In response to the global oil supply constraints that kept crude prices high, India released 5 million barrels of crude oil from its strategic reserves to cushion the impact of global oil price fluctuations³⁰. This move helped stabilize domestic fuel prices and ensured a continuous supply.

- **Negotiating Better Terms with Suppliers:** India engaged in active diplomacy to negotiate favourable terms with oil suppliers. This included seeking deferred payments and long-term contracts at stable prices. Also, India adeptly negotiated its oil imports to mitigate the impact of global price fluctuations and maintain its energy security. India, as a significant importer of oil, strategically increased its import of Russian oil, and then provide refined petroleum to other countries, including those in Europe. This manifested in both imports and exports, of petroleum products that helped maintained its Current Account Deficit.
- **Ramping Up Domestic Production:** Efforts were made to increase domestic production of oil and gas. India encouraged its national companies to expedite exploration and production activities.
- **Promoting Renewable Energy:** The crisis underscored the importance of transitioning to renewable energy sources. India accelerated its commitments to renewable energy, including solar and wind power, as part of its long-term energy security strategy³¹.
- **Energy Efficiency Measures:** The government promoted energy efficiency across various sectors to reduce overall consumption and dependence on imports.
- **Exploring Alternative Energy Sources:** India explored alternative energy sources, such as biofuels, hydrogen energy, and electric vehicles (EVs), to reduce dependence on fossil fuels.
- **Energy Diplomacy and Bilateral Agreements:** India engages in energy diplomacy by fostering bilateral agreements with energy-producing nations³². These agreements include long-term contracts for oil and gas supply, providing a degree of predictability and stability in energy imports. Strengthening diplomatic ties with energy-rich nations ensures a stable and consistent flow of energy resources.
- **Enhancing Regional Cooperation:** India engaged in regional cooperation for energy security, including initiatives under the International Solar Alliance and collaborations with neighbouring countries.

- **Food and Energy Security Measures:** To counter the global supply chain disruptions, especially in food and energy sectors, the government implemented measures to ensure domestic food security and explored alternative energy sources.
- **Global Supply Chain Realignment:** Recognizing the global supply chain disruptions caused by the conflict, India positioned itself as an alternative manufacturing and IT services hub³³.
- **International Collaborations:** India continued to engage with various countries and blocs to strengthen collaborations in areas like technology, healthcare, and infrastructure, aligning with its development goals.
- **Financial Measures:** The Reserve Bank of India and the government implemented measures to ensure financial stability and mitigate the impact of rising oil prices on the economy and currency exchange rates³⁴.

By employing these strategies, India managed to navigate the challenges posed by the Ukraine-Russia war on its energy security. This crisis also served as an impetus for India to accelerate its transition towards more sustainable and self-reliant energy sources.

Defence and Security Implications

In addition to the energy sector, the sanctions also had an impact on India's defence and technology sectors. Russia has long been a major supplier of defence equipment and technology to India, and the sanctions threatened to disrupt these crucial partnerships. While India continued its critical defence procurements from Russia withstanding pressures from US, including the S-400 missile defence system³⁵, vital for its national security it also started diversifying its sources of defence equipment and technology³⁶. The government managed this while navigating the threat of U.S. sanctions under CAATSA (Countering America's Adversaries Through Sanctions Act). India, also took steps to enhance its indigenous defence capabilities, reducing its dependence on imports from Russia and other countries affected by the sanctions.

Conclusion

Russia-Ukraine war presented a number of challenges for India, ranging from economic and geopolitical implications to security and humanitarian concerns. Through the Ukraine crisis, policies adopted by Modi government were largely pragmatic and focused on its national interests reflecting its commitment to strategic autonomy and the protection of India's economic and security interests in a complex international landscape.

In the last eighteen months since the Ukraine war broke out, India has been working to maintain its strong ties with both Russia and the West while also engaging with other countries to mitigate the impact of the sanctions. This balanced approach and skilful diplomacy allowed it to navigate the complex geopolitical landscape and maintain its economic stability despite the challenges posed by the sanctions.

India's strong and resilient economy too played a crucial role in helping the country overcome the challenges created by the sanctions on Russia. India's economic diversification and robust domestic market allowed it to absorb the shocks caused by the disruptions in its trade with Russia and its impact on global oil and gas prices. India's ability to overcome these challenges serves as a testament to its resilience and adaptability in the face of complex geopolitical and economic pressures.

As regards to India's dependence on Russian military hardware, while it continues to rely on Russian defence equipment, much of which is deeply integrated into its armed forces, India has consciously diversified its sources of defence procurement by engaging with the U.S. and other partners. Resolving India's overdependence on Russia for military hardware and managing the shift towards the U.S. will require a careful and calibrated approach. India will need to strike a delicate balance between maintaining its relationship with Russia and forging closer ties with the U.S., while also investing in the necessary infrastructure and capabilities to seamlessly integrate new equipment. This shift has the potential to strengthen India's defence capabilities and align its strategic interests with key partners in the Indo-Pacific region.

In conclusion, India's balanced and nuanced approach towards U.S. and Russia is a testament to its pragmatic foreign policy. As a major global player, India will need to continue to balance its relationships while safeguarding its own interests and stability.

End Notes

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